

Vibration Based Energy Harvester

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ABSTRACT

In the future, total main power resources reduction will happen. Sources such as petroleum and coal is reducing and market price getting jump. Therefore, study towards energy source from natural resource is increasingly preferred. Also attract researchers' attention is energy that based on from vibration which potential to be convert to a form of electrical energy. Study is carried out to identify the ability and method to increase energy production and effectiveness from the vibration source. Frequent with development of knowledge in studies towards smart electronic circuit, various methods identified applicable with this vibrational energy harvesting. Electronics circuit can increase total production of energy drastically and guarantee stability and energy density grouped. Three main factors that plays an important role in this study is transducer, adapter circuit and storage circuit. Adapter circuit do create huge different in energy production ability. For instance, by using MOSFET switch based rectifier could actually raised the the energy storing efficiency up to 90% compared to using conventional diode rectifier. Besides, the use of converter circuit and voltage vontroller application could increase the voltage output production 150% higher than the original input value. Hence energy produced can be reared. From the studies, various applications feasible which hoped able to compete with other natural energy harvester method existing like solar energy and wind energy.

Keywords: Smart energy harvester; Electronics circuitaries; Optimum energy storage

INTRODUCTION

Referring back to the history report, battery had become the portable energy source. Currently, with advancement of technology, wireless sensor network and low powered electronic device, turns the world demand toward alternative energy sources. The main focus is more to environment energy harvesting from vibration source which exists in daily life and maintaining the generated power with electronics circuitary.

Energy harvesting system that work efficiently usually is equipped with power adaptation module and storage element, which may be capacitor or rechargeable battery. Power adaptation circuit is needed because renewable source of energy usually does not produce regular voltage or and at irregular time that is different between frequency and power wave amplitude. Therefore, an important component in renewable energy technology is the need for energy adapter circuit between harvester mechanism and the storafe units in order to provide effective power management system.

Based on a study, vibrational energy harvesting concept is to change vibration into the form of electricity. Firstly vibration is change in relative motion between duplex use mass system and spring, it then turned into electricity with piezoelectric material help or other mechanical to electric energy converter material. As natural vibration generally have a low oscillating amplitude, hence mass usage is applied and spring generate oscillation phenomenon, strengthen relative movement amplitude compared to amplitude of vibration, improve the amount of harvested power [1].

Until this moment a few vibrational energy generator model was designed which mostly apply electronic circuit usage to enhance amount of energy capacity produced. Combination between rectifier circuit and current converter circuit is perceived as combination that is best for that purpose. One of the study seen very good to be studied is from another studies conducted, which had used rectifier circuit application and boost converter circuit. Figure 1 show system intended by researcher[2] .

Figure 1. Block diagram of the preferred energy harvester system

Block diagram for low voltage energy harvesting system is indicated in Figure 1. Natural vibrations in the form of mechanical energy changed to electric power by piezoelectric transducer. Outputs from transducer is alternating current voltage which will be transformed into direct current voltage and need to be multiplied its voltage value to a certain value that is sufficient to supply electronic load. Two levels which occurred during conversion process is rectification and boosting converter.

Although electronic circuit usage looks difficult and complex, however the application helped a lot to produce energy generator with high energy density. Study carried out by [3] is very suitable with need a energy harvester circuit. Which researcher drop make heavier lost power rate issue that is lowest and power extraction by maximum. One study of boost converter adaptation usage to maximize power output from piezoelectric device. It have found that in stimulation stage that is very high output power could be produced, rising totalled of 400% [4].

With the growth of research in power harvesting device has proved that total energy that is produced by piezoelectric materials not enough for supplying energy to high-powered electronic device. Therefore, for power harvesting technology pave the way into commercial market, energy accumulating method and storing harvsted energy to a certain amount of power that is sufficient can be achieved for portable electronic instrument usage, will be the key to success of energy harvesting system.

METHODOLOGY

In this study, design for vibrational energy harvester divided into three parts. First part is transducer which aim to convert energy that exists in natural vibration into electric power. The produced electricity is in the form of alternating current. Therefore, a need for rectifier circuit design which will convert alternating current to direct current. After that , another circuit that is important known as boost converter circuit which will increase output voltage value.

Figure 2. Method used for each harvester component

Energy conversion method chosen in this study is by using piezoelectric material. These materials change mechanical energy from pressure and vibration to electrical power. It can generate electrical charge when mechanical stress imposed on the body. Hence piezoelectric materials is confirmed by researchers as very effective to develop various harvesters with different application.

Rectifier circuit proposed is with the application of MOSFET switch operation. Firstly, MOSFET switching circuit full-wave rectifier that convert half negative wave to positive wave by reducing degrading of voltage and power consumption. This method is equivalent to diode rectifier circuit concept however more efficient in energy harvesting system implementation case. This is because, it's usage seems to reduce the gathered energy loss. This method is very suitable for energy harvester use which generate total internal energy that is minimal like vibrational energy from piezoelectric device.

Boost converter usage with energy harvester application is encouraged because of energy conversion efficiency that is high if compared to other method. Method that is proposed for the study is boost converter to achieve output voltage that is optimum and controlled. Power flow are controlled through PWM for MOSFET switching control in circuit from DC- DC converter. Single phase boost converter advantage is the used of a single MOSFET switching and because energy losses is smaller and suitable for energy harvesting application.

To evaluating piezoelectric energy harvester performance, experimental operation will be used. Function generator and amplifier used to handle exciter with various frequencies and acceleration, and electric circuit which contains load, capacitor, and rectifier is connected with harvester for impedance matching and output signal correction.

Figure 3. Complete circuit of vibration energy harvester

PZT bends when stress is imposed and produce a total of charge from the force e . Equivalent electric circuit for the energy harvester in represent with simulation using software Simulink / Matlab. PZT role is to receive pressure from stress through mechanical movement by vibrational energy, when PZT limbered, so charge will be free moving. Total harvested charge is stored, and delivered to power electric circuit. Intermediate with electronic circuit network will extract power and deliver it to energy storage device.

For the purpose of experiment to investigate energy harvesting ability, a few module is used. The module can help to generate energy from vibration and give information on energy that is generated. Energy harvesting kit is use for research purposes which contain piezoelectric plate(MFC). By flexing the cantilever will produce energy. In an effort to acquire energy product that is fixed and stable, frequency generator together with vibration amplifier is used.

Figure 4. Component used in experimental procedure

Piezoelectric material produces voltage or current that is proportional with pressure and frequency. This energy can be collected and applied according application rate that is suitable. Therefore, energy harvesting module is one of the mediator method between high impedance source and application. Smart micro control is used.

Figure 5. Energy harvesting module that is used

Next, control system for converter stimulation circuit will be implemented. Specifically, will implement what is so called as voltage mode controller for DC-DC converter where system is increases to a higher output voltage. Circuit illustration is indicated in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Closed circuit voltage output controller

Control in output voltage used to achieve voltage value that is accurate and avoid the occurrence of over or lower amount in output voltage value. PI controller used to control voltage signal after that it will send to PWM generator then PWM generator used to tune K_p and K_i values from PI controller.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Study for vibrational energy harvester divided into various parts and every study involved with each other. It is because every decision achieved will be used as parameter for further study. Study started by analyzing piezoelectric device in order to identify the energy conversion ability.

Result gained from experiment is very important which to obtain optimum frequency value and optimum amplitude to the system. The value is chosen so that system can produce a large amount of energy and consistent. Result obtained will further be used to study other components such as rectifier circuit study and converter circuit. Rectifier circuit used for energy harvester system should be systematic. Which able to convert high voltage amount and avoid losses to the internal energy.

Piezoelectric plate represented as energy producer from vibration sources however with internal amount of obstruction that distinctive. The energy source feature can be represented by internal resistance and idle voltage produced. However the harvester characteristics really have reliance with piezoelectric application and frequency. The certain parameters can be identified with the use of external resistance and voltage measuring unit.

Figure 7. Graph of energy output by PEH

Based on Figure 7, amount of energy produced is higher at frequency 15 Hz and amplitude in second stage. This is because in every vibration amplitude level, there is rate of frequency that is distinctive and accordingly to the PZT material and structure build, by which at the perfect pair of amplitude and frequency would produce greatest amount of charge. Besides, from the result above we can conclude that internal resistance value and load also play role in produced energy level. By observing Figure 7. At load resistance value 250 KΩ until 300 KΩ amount of energy produced is highest by system with frequency of 15 Hz.

To study rectifier circuit effectiveness to be used with vibrational energy generator system, two type of rectifier circuit were identified to be compared. First circuit is rectifier circuit using diode in full bridge continuation configuration and second circuit is rectifier circuit using four N-channel MOSFET and PWM usage to switch MOSFET switch.

Diode rectifier circuit usage is easy and cost saving. But diode circuit also generally have fastest reaction to negative voltage, then causes power losses that are high due to voltage decrease rate of forward negative positive junction which is equivalent to 0.7V. This power losses cause circuit temperature to increase, further cause the circuit to need heat management. Another disadvantage is diode have high reverse current rate as high as 1mA. Thus cause lost in power to the stored energy.

Replacing diode with MOSFET can reduce lost power significantly with eliminate diode rectifier device decrease in forward voltage. MOSFET has minimum voltage drop value.

Table 1. Rate of energy losses by rectifier circuit

Circuit types	Conduction losses	Power losses
Diode	$4 \times 0.7V \times 3.5A$	9.8 W
MOSFET	$4 \times 10m\Omega \times 3.5^2A$	0.49W

Table 1 compare the efficiency level of the two rectifier circuits using simple calculations. Rms current flow being recorded from circuit that is at value of 3.5 A and MOSFET used on the other hand has 10mΩ rintangannya. Clearly in the table above proved that lost power value in MOSFET rectifier circuit far lower compared to diode rectifier circuit. Managed to achieved almost 95% in power loss reduction by MOSFET rectifier circuit. Hence make MOSFET type rectifier to be most reliable for energy harvester purpose.

Next the study continues for direct current converter circuit usage. In many industrial application, it required to convert DC voltage source still into variable DC voltage source, DC-DC converter that directly convert from DC to DC and is known as DC converter. DC converter resembles AC converter, it could be used to improve DC voltage source value.

With Matlab simulation, the converter circuit is designed with input voltage at value 2 V and output voltage at value of 5 V. Output voltage is set to be at 5 V is because the total voltage that is most suitable for capacitor input. According to the capacitor feature, if input voltage exceed 5 V, capacitor will experience reduction in life span. Therefore calculation carried out to determine parameter for DC converter.

PI control circuit used which in purpose to prevent from output voltage instability and ensure output voltage value remained at 5 V although input voltage value is different.

Figure 8. Graft of ouput voltage by dc converter

Table 2. Result from boost converter simulation

Type of Circuit	Output Voltage (V)	Output Stability
Without controller circuit	2	Not stable
With controller circuit	5	Not stable
Boost converter+ PI controller	5	Stable

According to the above table, it is seen that output voltage after converter and controller effect is more stable and remained voltage value at value 5 V. Which originally without controller circuit the output voltage in early circuit is unstable and contain lot of ripple. The problem had been overcome with this method. With this method not only avoid voltage to change at random, even increase equipment life span in the system.

CONCLUSION AND IMPROVEMENT

This study discuss on vibrational energy harvester that is efficient which reduce losses rate in circuit also increase amount of energy that able to be generated. Two main highlight that is focussed for the purpose of improving this energy harvester performance is combination between rectifier circuit and boost converter circuit. Rectifier circuit for energy harvesting system suposely implement the application of MOSFET switch which can improve current conversion efficiency from alternating current to direct current. Apart from that MOSFET usage demonstrated high efficiency in reducing energy loss from reverse current flow or voltage reduction. Compared to the harvester system which use the use diode rectifier circuit, rectifier circuit using MOSFET switch can improve accumulated energy retention efficiency over 90%. Apart from that, boost converter circuit with PI control is a addition that perfectly fit for energy harvesting system. This due to converter circuit could play role like transformer for direct current by increasing output voltage value as much as 150%. For this harvester system improvement purpose, an addition in rectifier circuit seen as able to become a very good addition. Rectifier circuit proposed is with two levels operation. First stage is MOSFET switch full wave rectifier circuit that replace half negative wave to positive wave by reducing voltage decline and power consumption. The second level is to add a comparator circuit to work together with the rectifier. The camparator is used as vibration detector which detect the amount of voltage given by the PZT converter. The amount of voltage should be higher than the comparator based voltage in order to set the circuit on closed circuit hence connecting the whole circuit. While no energy is harvested from vibration, the camparator will be witch off and cut the connection from the energy storage circuit and rectifier circuit. Hence avoid any back current flow and energy loss to conduction.

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